

CARGO-ACT Data Management Plan

Version 1

Description

This plan describes management of data collected during the EU-funded CARGO-ACT project. The CARGO-ACT project intends to harmonize procedures and data management between U.S. American and European research infrastructures observing the properties of short-lived atmospheric constituents, i.e. aerosol particles, clouds, and reactive trace gases. This DMP doesn't cover management of data collected during normal operations of these infrastructures, only the data collected during the CARGO-ACT project.

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

Developing, consolidating and optimising the European research infrastructures landscape, maintaining global leadership (2023) (HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01)

Researchers

Ewan O'Connor (orcid:0000-0001-9834-5100), Shridhar Jawak (orcid:0000-0002-0648-3109), LUCIA MONA (orcid:0000-0003-4157-

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Organizations

Norwegian Institute for Air Research (NILU), Kjeller, Norway, National Institute for Research and Development in Optoelectronics INOE 2000, Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy, Leibniz Institute for Tropos (replace), Brookhaven National Laboratory, University of Helsinki - Department of Physics, United States Department of Commerce, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, Earth System Research Laboratory, Global Monitoring Laboratory, University of Boulder, Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences, Oak Ridge National Laboratory - Environmental Science Divison, CNRS, Pacific Northwest National Laboratory, UNI: NASA Goddard Space Flight Center Gree nbelt USA, University of Maryland, Baltimore County, Finnish Meteorological Institute

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [CARGO-ACT Data Management Plan](#)

Description:

This plan describes management of data collected during the EU-funded CARGO-ACT project. The CARGO-ACT project intends to harmonize procedures and data management between U.S. American and European research infrastructures observing the properties of short-lived atmospheric constituents, i.e. aerosol particles, clouds, and reactive trace gases. This DMP doesn't cover management of data collected during normal operations of these infrastructures, only the data collected during the CARGO-ACT project.

Researchers:

[Ewan O'Connor \(orcid:0000-0001-9834-5100\)](#)

[Shridhar Jawak \(orcid:0000-0002-0648-3109\)](#)

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Organizations:

[Norwegian Institute for Air Research \(NILU\), Kjeller, Norway](#)

[National Institute for Research and Development in Optoelectronics INOE 2000](#)

[Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy](#)

[Leibniz Institute for Tropos \(replace\)](#)

[Brookhaven National Laboratory](#)

[University of Helsinki - Department of Physics](#)

[United States Department of Commerce, National Oceanic and Atmospheric](#)

[Administration, Earth System Research Laboratory, Global Monitoring Laboratory](#)

[University of Boulder, Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences](#)

[Oak Ridge National Laboratory - Environmental Science Divison](#)

[CNRS](#)

[Pacific Northwest National Laboratory](#)

[UNI: NASA Goddard Space Flight Center Gree nbelt USA](#)

[University of Maryland, Baltimore County](#)

[Finnish Meteorological Institute](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: Developing, consolidating and optimising the European research infrastructures landscape, maintaining global leadership (2023) (HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01)

Project: CARGO-ACT

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Software

The project may produce software. The software will be archived and version controlled in Github. The plug-in to Zenodo will be used to identify the software and software versions.

Template: Horizon Europe

Type: Dataset

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Software

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The software generated in the project is by definition generated within the scope of the current project. The reuse of existing data isn't relevant here.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

The software will constitute primary data generated by the project.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Containers: TAR, GZIP, ZIP, also explicit code in Python or other languages.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

50MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To keep on record

Software is essential documentation of a project and should be kept on record.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The software and codes are produced manually by humans.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education

The software will be interesting mainly for environmental research infrastructures or networks focusing on observations of air quality and climate-relevant atmospheric parameters.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Other

DOI

Software produced in the project will be archived in ZENODO, and will be associated with the "CARGO-ACT" community

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Zenodo uses DOIs issued by DataCite, thus uses the DataCite metadata schema.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Reference

According to the [DataCite schema](#).

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

DataCite vocabulary

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://github.com/metadatascenter/datacite-controlled-vocabulary>

DataCite vocabulary is obligatory to fill in the DataCite schema.

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Registry/Catalogue

Zenodo catalogue.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

From Zenodo APIs.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Zenodo is a widely-used open repository for digital resources.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports back up
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Follows metadata standards

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

Zenodo is recommended by FAIRsharing.org.

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Uses DataCite to resolve identifiers.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Title of the software

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Zenodo is open.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through Zenodo web-interface or API.

Accessing persons aren't identified.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

unlimited duration.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Use Zenodo's access mechanisms

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

According to DataCite schema.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

According to Zenodo DMP.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

DataCite vocabulary.

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

Vocabulary is pre-existing

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

Zenodo's metadata interface.

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

Specified by Zenodo as described In [Zenodo's data FAIRness self-assessment](#).

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

References by PID, e.g DOI.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

- Creative Commons Attribution 4.0
- GNU Affero General Public License v3

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Other

Software is quality assured project internally. Data are archived together with references to the software used to produce them. New software versions trigger new data versions.

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Authors are specified in documents. Data are archived together with references to the software used to produce them. New software versions trigger new data versions.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Set up of scientific and technical committee

Project internal review.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

100

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

- Re-use
- Security

Indirect cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Infrastructure Grant

Project.

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Firewall
- Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

Data storage

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Zenodo is a long-term archive.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Milestones and deliverables

The project will produce Deliverables and Milestones documenting project progress and results. These are archived in PDF format, which is openly accessible. To meet the identification and version history criteria, the documents will be archived in the [Zenodo general purpose archive](#). Access will be regulated according to the nature of the document, with open access as default.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Protocols

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The Milestones and Deliverables, are by definition generated in the project. Re-use of existing data isn't relevant here.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

The text documents will constitute primary data generated by the project.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Portable Document Format (PDF)

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

4MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To keep on record

Milestones and deliverable are essential documentation of project progress, and should be kept on record.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The text documents, here milestones and deliverables, are produced manually by humans.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Research communities
- Education
- Other

The project results will be interesting mainly for environmental research infrastructures or networks focusing on observations of air quality and climate relevant atmospheric parameters.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Other

DOI

Text documents produced in the project will be archived in ZENODO, and will be associated with the "CARGO-ACT" community

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Zenodo uses DOIs issued by DataCite, thus uses the DataCite metadata schema.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Reference

According to DataCite schema.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

DataCite vocabulary

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://github.com/metadacenter/datacite-controlled-vocabulary>

DataCite vocabulary is obligatory to fill in DataCite schema.

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Registry/Catalogue

Zenodo catalogue.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

From Zenodo APIs.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Zenodo is a widely-used open repository for digital resources.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports back up
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Follows metadata standards

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

Zenodo is recommended by [FAIRsharing.org](https://fairsharing.org).

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Uses DataCite to resolve identifiers.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Title of deliverable / milestone.

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Zenodo is open.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through Zenodo web-interface or API.

Accessing persons aren't identified.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

unlimited duration.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Use Zenodo's access mechanisms

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

According to DataCite schema.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

According to Zenodo DMP.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

DataCite vocabulary.

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

Vocabulary is pre-existing

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

Zenodo's metadata interface.

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

Specified by Zenodo.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

References by PID, e.g DOI.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Other

Documents are quality assured project internally.

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Authors are specified in documents. They are also identified in the Zenodo metadata schema, identified by PID, which makes the information machine actionable.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Set up of scientific and technical committee

Project internal review, according to standard rules of scientific review.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

100

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

Indirect cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Infrastructure Grant

Project.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Markus Fiebig (orcid: [0000-0002-3380-3470](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3380-3470))

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Firewall
- Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

Data storage

Zenodo is a certified archive, and should therefore have backup measures in place.

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Zenodo is a long-term archive.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Quality assurance specifications

The project will produce text documents specifying quality assurance specifications. These are archived in PDF format, which is openly accessible. The documents will be archived in the [Zenodo](#) (general purpose archive) to meet the identification and version history criteria. Access will be regulated according to the nature of the document, with open access as default.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Protocols

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The text documents described here include specifications of quality assurance procedures, i.e.

data treatment procedures, measurement guidelines, standard operating procedures, and technical requirements . These protocols are by definition generated in the project. The reuse of existing data isn't relevant here.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

The text documents will constitute primary data generated by the project.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Portable Document Format (PDF)

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

4MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To keep on record

Lab calibration protocols/procedures are essential documentation for the project's progress and should be kept on record.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The text documents, here QA specifications, are produced manually by humans.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education
- Other

The project results will be interesting mainly for environmental research infrastructures or networks focusing on observations of air quality and climate relevant atmospheric parameters.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Other

DOI

Text documents produced in the project will be archived in [ZENODO](#), and will be associated with the "CARGO-ACT" project community

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Zenodo uses DOIs issued by DataCite, thus uses the DataCite metadata schema.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Reference

According to DataCite schema.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

DataCite vocabulary

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://github.com/metadatascenter/datacite-controlled-vocabulary>

DataCite vocabulary is obligatory to fill in DataCite schema.

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Registry/Catalogue

Zenodo catalogue.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

From Zenodo APIs.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Zenodo is a widely-used open repository for digital resources.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports back up
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Follows metadata standards

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

Zenodo is recommended by [FAIRsharing.org](https://fairsharing.org).

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Uses DataCite to resolve identifiers.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Title of lab calibration protocol

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Zenodo is open.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through Zenodo web-interface or API.

Accessing persons aren't identified.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

unlimited duration.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Use Zenodo's access mechanisms

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

According to DataCite schema.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

According to Zenodo DMP.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

DataCite vocabulary.

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

Vocabulary is pre-existing

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

Zenodo's metadata interface.

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

Specified by Zenodo.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

References by PID, e.g DOI.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Other

Documents are quality assured project internally.

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Authors are specified in documents.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Set up of scientific and technical committee

Project internal review.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

100

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

Indirect cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Infrastructure Grant

Project.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Markus Fiebig (orcid: [0000-0002-3380-3470](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3380-3470))

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Firewall
- Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

Data storage

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Zenodo is a long-term archive.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Intercomparisons on ambient air

The project will conduct intercomparisons of observations on atmospheric properties and constituents in the ambient, conducted by the US networks and ACTRIS as European RI. The data collected during these intercomparison campaigns will be archived in the responsible units of the ACTRIS Data Centre or the ARM Data Center.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The intercomparison campaigns will generate new data.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

The intercomparison campaigns will conduct atmospheric ambient air observations.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Observation specific, mostly converted to NetCDF-CF data format during data curation.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

10 GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To keep on record

Keep record for demonstrating comparability and provenance of observations conducted in US and European networks for observing short-lived atmospheric constituents.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Observations during intercomparison campaigns

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

Researchers will be able to assess accuracy and comparability of data across regional networks.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

ACTRIS DC and ARM DC use DOIs to identify data. The default granularity resolves data streams from individual instruments. Once data collection and curation are completed, a [collection DOI](#) for all intercomparison data generated in CARGO-ACT can be generated.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

ACTRIS DC and ARM DC use DOIs provided by DataCite.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

DataCite vocabulary, ACTRIS vocabulary.

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://github.com/metadatascenter/datacite-controlled-vocabulary>;
https://vocabulary.actris.nilu.no/actris_vocab/

DataCite vocabulary is obligatory to fill in the DataCite schema. ACTRIS vocabulary is used in addition for domain specific purposes.

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

Metadata are searchable both in ACTRIS Data Portal and ACTRIS metadata API, and in the corresponding APIs of the ARM Data Center

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Metadata are searchable through ACTRIS and ARM metadata APIs.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

- a. ACTRIS Data Centre
- b. ARM Data Center

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

No

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

ACTRIS Data Centre is part of the project, and intends to work on obtaining CoreTrustSeal certification. ARM Data Center is already CoreTrustSeal certified.

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Repositories provide DOI landing pages.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Title format depends on data type

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

ACTRIS Data Centre doesn't use access restrictions.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

No committee needed since data are open.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

As long as ACTRIS and ARM Data Centres exist, i.e. at least for the next 20 years.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Other

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

To ensure attribution of the infrastructure

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Metadata contain data access points in various protocols.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

DataCite vocabulary, ACTRIS vocabulary

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

ACTRIS vocabulary: https://vocabulary.actris.nilu.no/actris_vocab/

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

ENVRI atmospheric domain FAIRness implementation plan.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

References are under implementation.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

- Creative Commons Attribution 4.0
- CC0 1.0

No embargo planned.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Data cleaning

- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

The ACTRIS Data Centre exists as long as the ACTRIS infrastructure exists, and will keep the data available after the project end. Same for ARM.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

No

Provenance documentation is under implementation.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

500

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

Indirect cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Infrastructure Grant

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Cathrine Lund Myhre (orcid: [0000-0003-3587-5926](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3587-5926))

Head of ACTRIS Date Centre

b. LUCIA MONA (orcid: [0000-0003-4157-0838](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4157-0838))

Head of ACTRIS Date Centre Aerosol Remote Sensing unit

c. Ewan O'Connor (orcid: [0000-0001-9834-5100](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9834-5100))

Head of ACTRIS Date Centre Cloud Remote Sensing unit

d. Markus Fiebig (orcid: [0000-0002-3380-3470](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3380-3470))

Head of ACTRIS Date Centre In Situ unit

e. Cathy Boone (orcid: [0000-0003-2972-2851](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2972-2851))

Head of ACTRIS Date Centre Trace Gas Remote Sensing unit

f. Giri Prakash

Head of ARM Data Center.

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Firewall
- Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access

- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

ACTRIS DC has the same lifetime as the ACTRIS Research Infrastructure, similar for ARM.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

EBAS

EBAS is a database hosting observation data of atmospheric chemical composition and physical properties. EBAS hosts data submitted by data originators in support of a number of national and international programs ranging from monitoring activities to research projects. EBAS is developed and operated by the Norwegian Institute for Air Research (NILU). We hope the information found on the web-site is self explanatory, and we would particularly ask you to consider the text found in the data disclaimer and in the “info” pages associated to the filter criteria.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

10 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers

- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- The public

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Schema 4.7

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Statistical
- Legal

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

ACTRIS vocabulary.

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

https://vocabulary.actris.nilu.no/actris_vocab/

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

31301 Atmospheric Science

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

By using RestAPI.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

EBAS

EBAS

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports withdrawal
- Supports back up

- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Follows metadata standards
- Uses non-proprietary formats
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Follows curation processes

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

The repository is hosted by a project partner.

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Identifiers resolve to landing pages which link to data access endpoints in several protocols.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

EBAS

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Data remain accessible along with the other content of EBAS.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

No fixed limit.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Other

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

CC BY 4 is used to ensure visibility of data centre as metadata source.

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

ACTRIS vocabulary.

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

https://vocabulary.actris.nilu.no/actris_vocab/

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

Yes

Metadata are available in ISO19115 with WMO profile.

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

ENVRI atmospheric domain best practices.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Data cleaning
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards
- Other

Sanity checks included.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

500

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Markus Fiebig (orcid: [0000-0002-3380-3470](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3380-3470))

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Ensuring continuous operation of archive.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Atmospheric Radiation Measurement (ARM) Data Center

The Atmospheric Radiation Measurement Data Center (ADC) is a long-term archive and distribution facility for various ground-based, aerial and model data products in support of atmospheric and climate research.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The ARM Data Center manages and archives original observations connected with the atmospheric radiation budget.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

The ARM Data Center archives primary data.

1.1.5 What is its format?

NetCDF is the preferred file format.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

15MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Original observations in the atmosphere

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- Economy
- The public

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

CF (Climate and Forecast) Metadata Conventions

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Legal

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Climate Forecast convention Standard Names, GCMD, Schema.org are used.

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

a. <https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/data/tools/gcmd-keyword-viewer>

Global Change Master Directory Keywords

b. <https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/data/tools/gcmd-keyword-viewer>

Global Change Master Directory Keywords

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Registry/Catalogue

<https://adc.arm.gov/discovery/>

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

31301 Atmospheric Science

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

HTTPS, FTP, OPeNDAP, REST API

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

ARM Data Center

<https://adc.arm.gov/discovery/>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

Has certification

3.2.1.3 Add certification(s)

CoreTrustSeal

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Yes.

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Shared

Open access

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

no embargo period.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

Climate Forecast Convention, GCMD, Schema.org, NetCDF 1.7

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

Data are available in NetCDF format by HTTPS, FTP, OPeNDAP.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

200

US Dollar

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Giri Prakash

Head of ARM Data Center

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Yes.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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